

JAVASCRIPTDA O'ZGARUVCHILAR

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Anotatsiya: JavaScript da o'zgaruvchilar mavzusini tushuntirishga qaratilgan. Bu erda o'zgaruvchilar nima ekanligi, qanday e'lon qilinishi va qanday ishlatilishi haqida ma'lumot beriladi. Shuningdek, turli usullar orasidagi farqlar va ularning afzalliklari va kamchiliklari ham bayon etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: JavaScript, o'zgaruvchi, var, let, const, e'lon qilish, ishlatish.

JavaScript dasturlash tilida o'zgaruvchilar muhim qavramlardan biridir. O'zgaruvchilar, ma'lum bir qiymatni saqlash va uni dastur ichida ishlatish imkonini beradi. Bu tezisda JavaScript o'zgaruvchilarining asosiy turlari va ulardan foydalanish usullari haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan. JavaScriptda o'zgaruvchilarning turlari dinamik tip bo'lib, o'zgaruvchiga dastur ichida qiymat berilganda JavaScript avtomatik ravishda to'g'ridan-to'g'ri o'zgaruvchi turini aniqlaydi. O'zgaruvchilar uchun avval var, let yoki const kalit so'zlari bilan o'zgaruvchi nomi ta'riflanadi.

var: Bu kalit so'z orqali o'zgaruvchilar ta'riflanishida ishlatiladi. Ustunliklaridan biri, o'zgaruvchini dastur ichidagi barcha joylarda ishlatish imkonini beradi. Masalan:

```
var myVariable = "Salom, JavaScript!";
```

let: ES6 (ECMAScript 2015) standartlari bilan kiritilgan yangilik. O'zgaruvchini let kalit so'zi bilan ta'riflashga imkon beradi. Bundan tashqari, let orqali ta'riflangan o'zgaruvchilar blokning ichida bo'lgan chegaralarini saqlaydi:

```
let myVariable = "Salom, JavaScript!";
```

const: Bu kalit so'z orqali o'zgaruvchilar ta'riflanishi, o'zgarmas (immutable) qiymatni ta'riflash uchun ishlatiladi. O'zgaruvchi const bilan ta'riflandikdan keyin o'zgartirib bo'lmaydi:

```
const myVariable = "Salom, JavaScript!";
```

O'zgaruvchilarni JavaScript dasturlashida foydalanishning bir qismini ta'riflashning hammasidan oldin ko'rish juda muhim. Agar o'zgaruvchi dastur ichida e'lon qilinmasa, uni foydalanishdan oldin JavaScript xatosi yuzaga keladi. O'zgaruvchi nomi quyidagi qoidalarga amal qilishi kerak:

O'zgaruvchi nomi harf (a-z, A-Z) yoki pastki chiziq (_) bilan boshlanishi kerak.

Keyingi harf sifatida harf, raqam (0-9) yoki pastki chiziq ishlatish mumkin.

O'zgaruvchi nomida bo'sh joylar yoki belgilar (masalan, -, *, @) bo'lishi mumkin emas.

O'zgaruvchi nomlari katta-kichik xarflar bilan farq qiladi (masalan, myVariable va myvariable ikkalasi ham farqli).

JavaScript o'zgaruvchilarida qiymatlar turli turlarda bo'lishi mumkin. Quyidagi turli o'zgaruvchi qiymatlari JavaScriptda foydalaniladigan eng mashhurlaridandir:

Sonlar: JavaScriptda butun sonlar va o'nlik sonlar (decimal) ko'p mavjud. Sonlarni o'zgaruvchiga tayinlash uchun ularni to'g'ri ravishda yozishingiz mumkin. Misol uchun:

```
var age = 25;
```

```
var price = 9.99;
```

Matnlar (string): Matn qiymatlarini yozish uchun o'zgaruvchi qiymati qo'lga kiritilgan matnning orasiga yoziladi. Matnlarni tirnoshda yoki ikki tirnoshda ifodalash mumkin. Misol uchun:

```
var name = "John";
```

```
var message = 'Salom, dunyo!';
```

Mantiqiy qiymatlar (boolean): Mantiqiy qiymatlar true (rost) va false (yolg'on) bo'lishi mumkin. O'zgaruvchi qiymati shartlar, loyihalar bilan ishlash va boshqalar kabi holatlarda foydalaniladi. Misol uchun:

```
var isActive = true;
```

```
var isLoggedIn = false;
```

Massivlar (arrays): Massivlar bir nechta qiymatlarni to'plab turadi. O'zgaruvchiga massivni tayinlash uchun [] belgilaridan foydalaniladi va har bir element matn, son yoki boshqa turdagi ma'lumot bo'lishi mumkin. Misol uchun:

```
var numbers = [1, 2, 3, 4, 5];
```

```
var fruits = ["Apple", "Banana", "Orange"];
```

Ob'ektlar (objects): Ob'ektlar bir nechta xususiyat va uning qiymatlari to'plamidir. Ob'ektlarni yaratish uchun { } belgilaridan foydalaniladi va xususiyat nomi va uning qiymati orasida : ishlatiladi. Misol uchun:

```
var person = {
```

```
  name: "John",
```

```
  age: 25,
```

```
  city: "London"
```

```
};
```

JavaScriptda boshqa turli o'zgaruvchi turlari ham mavjud, masalan, null (bo'sh qiymat), undefined (aniq qiymat bo'lmagan) va boshqalar. O'zgaruvchilarni to'g'ridan-to'g'ri qiymatlar bilan birlashtirish, ularga aloqador operatorlardan foydalanish, funksiyalarni va dasturlarni ishlatish mumkin. O'zgaruvchilarning foydalanishini JavaScript dasturlashning asosiy qoidalari va tamoyillarini tushuntirib beradi.

Xulosa

JavaScript da o'zgaruvchilar ma'lumotlarni saqlash uchun muhim rol o'ynaydi. O'zgaruvchilarni e'lon qilishning turli usullari bor bo'lib, ularning har biri o'ziga xos xususiyatlarga ega. O'zgaruvchilarni to'g'ri va samarali ishlatish dasturlash jarayonini soddalashtiradi va kodni optimallashtiradi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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